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Research Article

**AN EXPERIMENTAL CONTROL RESEARCH TO ASCERTAIN
THE BOTTOM EFFECTS OF HOMOCYSTEINE ON THE
MEASUREMENT OF BONE MASS****¹Dr. Iqra Sagheer, ²Dr. Farwa Iqbal, ³Dr. Rehma Abdul Hameed**
¹Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore**Abstract**

Objectives: To ascertain whether homocysteine is unblameable or the actual participant in affecting bone. The study aimed at getting to the bottom of the effect of homocysteine on bone mass measurement.

Methodology: This study of experimental-control category organized between December 2016 to November 2017 at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad includes 30 standard patients having a normal bone mass measurement with an equal number of subjects having at least one yardstick for measuring the density of osteoporosis in femur neck or coccyx vertebrae. Subjects of the two categories compared on the basis of sex and age. Bone mass measurement calculated by DXA and fasting antidote homocysteine quantity calculated by EIA kits in all qualified subjects.

Results: Average individual values of antidote measure of homocysteine were 11.970 ± 03.09 and 11.670 ± 04.38 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ in control and experimental categories. The difference ($p=0.7610$) of the values of the two categories was not that big. There was no significant connection in the experimental and control categories of antidote homocysteine measure and bone mass measurement. The values were as: coccyx vertebrae in control category ($r=0.0250$, $p=0.90$), coccyx vertebrae in experimental category ($r=0.0710$, $p=0.7160$), femur cervix in control category ($r=0.2760$, $p=0.1470$), femur cervix in experimental category ($r=0.0010$, $p=0.9980$).

Conclusion: In spite of a lot of research about the consequence of homocysteine on the escalated possibility of fractures caused by osteoporosis, our study did not reveal the link between antidote measure of homocysteine and bone mass measurement. Due to the massive number of elements influencing the density of bone, ending deductions need immense considerations with attention paid to other astonishing factors.

Keywords: Bone Mass Measurement, Femur Neck, Coccyx Vertebrae, Homocysteine and Osteoporosis.

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INTRODUCTION:

Porous bone is the most usual metabolous bone disease and includes 1/3rd of women and 1/8th of men [1]. One of the perfect and fruitful neutralization attitudes to this growing and widespread health issue is counteraction through spotting and eradication of healable germ elements. One of the elements which have gauged the concentration of scientists is homocysteine. Despite huge research in this discipline, a lot more work is required in this field for accurate results, due to the massive number of elements that affect bone life [2].

Despite the fact that homocysteine can't be in the diet of human but it is an important intermediary in 2-amino-4-(methylthio) butanoic acid change in mammals [3]. The worse density of osteoporosis was seen in victims of homocysteinemia for the first time (in these patients antidote quantity of homocysteine is elevated) [4]. High antidote quantity of homocysteine is the agent for confusion in scleroprotein chemical bonding, which leads to the thinness of the bone matrix [5-7]. These conclusions are taken from the patients of homocysteinemia or with MTHFR genetic variation (imperfect homocysteine biological process). Few types of research have concluded that in standard population the antidote measure of homocysteine doesn't hit a

top level as homocysteinemia, and cannot attacks bone matrix [8].

METHODOLOGY:

This study of experimental control groups organized between December 2016 to November 2017 at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad. Experimental category consisted of 30 patients having osteoporosis on the basis of WHO interpretation of bone mineral density groups [11] at least one yardstick in femur cervix or coccyx vertebrae domain. Control category consisted of 30 patients with normal BMD. Patients compared for sex and age. All patients enquired about the extent of physical tasks and everyday sun exposure. A short record about diet obtained including milk, coffee, eggs etc. People with normal nutritional styles rejected from the study. Smoking habits were also unfolded.

Bone mineral density calculated by DXA and fasting antidote homocysteine quantity calculated by EIA kit (DRG Diagnostics, USA). In the experimental category, prime inclusion aspect was major osteoporosis. Subjects having minor osteoporosis and a record of medications altering bone thickness also rejected. Ethics department validated the study. Results assessed as material when P's figure was less than 0.050.

Table – I: Contrast between variables in experimental and control

Factor	Control Category	Experimental Category	P-Figure
Age	59.960±9.750	62.900±11.630	0.2950
Age of first menstrual cycle	13.860±1.010	14.620±1.140	0.0170
Climacteric age	47.410±4.77	48.760±5.470	0.4670
Mass(kg)	72.930±11.940	63.310±9.870	0.0010
Stature tallness(cm)	156.00±8.190	152.240±4.660	0.0350
BMI (kg/m²)			
Male gender	6	1	
Female gender	24	29	0.1030
Day-to-day milk intake	7(14.10%) *	8(26.70%)	
	7(14.10%) **	12(40.0%)	0.3060
	15(51.80%) ***	10(33.30%)	
Exertion	11(36.70%) +	26(86.070%)	0
	19(63.30%) ++	4(3.130%)	
	6(20.0%) ^	15(50.0%)	0.0150
Day-to-day sun contact	24(80.0%) ^^	15(50.0%)	
Antidote homocysteine measure(imol/l)	11.670±9.750	11.970±3.090	0.7610
High blood cholesterol§	8(26.70%)	14(46.70%)	0.1080

P<0.050 assessed as material, *blow 03 glass/7 days, ** three to seven glass/7 days, *** more than seven glass/7days, +routine housework ++high-level exertion, ^<15.0min/24 hours, ^^>15.0min/24 hours, § low-density lipoproteins greater than 130.0mg/dl, TG greater than 150.0, high-density lipoproteins less than 40.0 for

men and less than 50.0 for women.

RESULTS:

The average age of total patients was 61.430 ± 0.75 yrs. The average age of first menstrual cycle was 14.280 ± 1.240 yrs. Average climacteric age was 48.340 ± 5.240 yrs. The individual percentage of homocysteine was 9(53.30%) and 14(70.0%) in the control and experimental categories. The difference ($p=0.7610$) of the average individual values of antidote measure of homocysteine between control (11.970 ± 03.09) and experimental (11.670 ± 04.38)

groups was not that big. There was no significant connection between experimental and control categories of antidote homocysteine measure and bone mass measurement.

To avoid the effects of non-identical factors, variables which have exhibited the very big difference between 2 categories were included in a multivariable evaluation (for the identification of individualistic effectual variables).

Figure – I: Relation between antidote measure of homocysteine and Bone Mineral Content of coccyx vertebrae in control category

Figure – II: Relation between antidote measure of homocysteine and Bone Mineral Content of coccyx vertebrae in the experimental category

DISCUSSION:

Presently, homocysteine is a threat to cause heart related and vascular occlusion diseases. Other researches exhibit the consequences of this new component in other disorders e.g. nervous system diseases, malignant anaemic cases, kidney failure, thyroid disorders, cancer and few skin signs of rheumatic diseases [13 – 16]. The issue that has freshly gauge high attention is the function of hyperhomocysteinemia in fractures attributable to

osteoporosis. Despite a number of researches had performed in this aspect because of wide-ranging reactions of this amalgam with few other bone's biotic elements, accurate and relevant outcomes were not available [10, 17 – 19].

In individual studies, Van Meurs, Janson and McLean have expressed that increasing antidote homocysteine can raise the chance of breakage attributable to osteoporosis [4, 16]. In an

investigation of 433 sick persons with a past record of the brain, attack figured out that homocysteine is an agent for pelvis breakage among others, in brain attack victims.

Dhonukshe-Rutten analyzed 1267 sick persons in the Netherlands and concluded that homocysteine presence has elevated the danger of bone breakage rate but no connection with bone mass density found. Investigations by Herman, Willadsen, Browner and Cagnacci didn't show the connection between bone mass density and antidote measures of homocysteine [19].

Few types of research show that the thing that results in breakage of bones in some victims was not hyperhomocysteinemia but lack of some additional nutrition, for instance, acide folique and water-soluble vitamins which are the principal root. Antidote measure of homocysteine can be a hint of similar nutritional insufficiencies [4].

In a research by Gulbahar and others consisting of 271 climacteric women of Iran bone mass

measurements at the femoral neck and coccyx vertebrae were related with the fraction of overall plasma homocysteine materially as well as in a negative way. BMD at coccyx vertebrae related with circulating folic acid in plasma. There was no relation found between methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase array with BMD at the femoral neck and coccyx vertebrae. The adverse relation of overall plasma homocysteine with BMD was insignificant when rectified for folic acid and cyanocobalamin [19].

Winding-up, our research can't exhibit a relation between antidote measure of homocysteine and bone mineral density. As mentioned before a number of elements attack bone thickness. So, the ending result of the research requires a lot more exploration with regard given to other influencing elements. Principal downside of this research was its small-scale sampling. We suggest like appraisal with large-scale sampling and extended researches for clarifying the part of antidote measure of homocysteine on bone breakage.

Figure – III: Relation between antidote measure of homocysteine and bone mineral density of femur neck in control category

Figure – IV: Relation between antidote homocysteine measure and bone mineral density of femur neck in the experimental category.

CONCLUSION:

In spite of a lot of research about the consequence of homocysteine on the escalated possibility of fractures caused by osteoporosis, our study did not reveal the link between antidote measure of homocysteine and bone mass measurement. Due to the massive number of elements influencing the density of bone, ending deductions need immense considerations with attention paid to other astonishing factors.

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